

USING MODERN TECHNOLOGY TO TEACH LISTENING TO YOUNG LEARNERS

Arazdurdiyeva Annasoltan Narbayevna

Student of the Faculty of Foreign Languages English Language and Literature Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

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ABSTRACT

In this article we will briefly focus on how we try to develop listening skills with our young learners who are learning English as an additional language.

Listening is the language modality that is used more frequently. It has been estimated that youth spend almost half their communication time listening, and students may receive as much as most of their in-school information through listening to teachers and to one another. Through listening, learners brain can analyze information quickly. For instance, the music in our daily lives or the news and information we hear on the radio, reach us faster than we see or read. Nowadays, the development of listening in young learners remains one of the most peak issues. Therefore teaching listening to young people is more important than other language skills. When we teach listening we allow students to follow directions, understand expectations, and make sense of oral communication. As children improve as listeners, they learn to use the same strategies to improve their command of the other language is so much more than simply understanding what someone is saying. We listen to different people in

different ways depending on how, where and when we are interacting, or whether we are interacting at all. Learners typically listen to three different sources of information in their lessons: the teacher, each other and, most commonly, an audio recording of one or two people speaking. To accomplish this goal, instructors focus on the process of listening rather than on its product.

1. They develop students' awareness of the listening process and listening strategies by asking students to think and talk about how they listen in their native language.

2. They allow students to practice the full repertoire of listening strategies by using authentic listening tasks.

3. They behave as authentic listeners by responding to student communication as a listener rather than as a teacher.

4. When working with listening tasks in class, they show students the strategies that will work best for the listening purpose and the type of text. They explain

how and why students should use the strategies.

5. They have students practice listening strategies in class and ask them to practice outside of class in their listening assignments. They encourage students to be conscious of what they're doing while they complete listening tape assignments.

6. They encourage students to evaluate their comprehension and their strategy use immediately after completing an assignment. They build comprehension checks into in-class and out-of-class listening assignments, and periodically review how and when to use particular strategies.

7. They encourage the development of listening skills and the use of listening strategies by using the target language to conduct classroom business: making announcements, assigning homework, describing the content and format of tests.

8. They do not assume that students will transfer strategy use from one task to another.

The explicitly mention how a particular strategy can be used in a different type of listening task or with another skill.

As a relevance researcher, I would like to dwell on the tasks of the topic. Firstly, the teacher should support children's understanding more effectively. If they direct their pupils attention to specific

points that have to be listened for using activities that actively support learners' understanding and guide their attention to specific parts of the spoken text.

- Some considerations for classroom listening

1. Give the children confidence. We should not expect them to always understand every word and they should know this.

2. Explain why the children have to listen. Make sure learners are clear about why they are listening, what the main point or purpose of the activity.

3. Help children develop specific strategies for listening. An important strategy that the teacher should teach is intelligent guesswork. Pupils are used to drawing on their background knowledge to work out something they are not sure.

Conclusion

Listening is an active process, as the mind actively engages in making meaning. It is therefore our duty as teachers to ensure that the materials we use are comprehensible to our young learners, as well as within the range of what they are developmentally ready for. Listening is also hard work. And can be stressful. So in order to maximize the potential for acquisition of language, we need to ensure that our young learners are not stressed about this process.

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